

FEEDBACK FOR TEACHING REFLECTION: HOW IT CAN MAKE A DIFFERENCE IN TEACHING PROGRESS

Qobiljonova Mukhlisa Kamilovna

Student: Faculty of English philology, Uzbekistan State

World Languages University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

mukhlisakabilzanova77@gmail.com

Scientific adviser: **Ziyodullayeva Aziza Akmalovna**

ESL teacher of Uzbekistan State World Languages University

at Faculty of English philology, Tashkent Uzbekistan

lia814982@gmail.com

Abstract: The sources and basic principles of teacher feedback will be tackled in this article. The article's approach to feedback explains how education processes. In addition to a teacher's and student's method of interaction, the article examines the impact of feedback on learning and accomplishments as well as one's personal development and support.

Key words: reflection, suitable criticism, personal development, process of learning, methods, and performance assessment

Introduction

Nowadays, both educators and learners who utilize feedback in their daily lives are intrigued by these challenges. Reflection and feedback are aspects of the same thing. They support one another in the process of personal growth. The task of reflection requires learners as well as educators thinking critically about an educational context or activity, maintaining its development, and assessing its result. It will and ought to develop either before, during, or thereafter a situation. Additionally, feedback has a big impact on performance and education and may greatly improve both teaching and learning. One of the main components of high-quality instruction is providing constructive criticism on the work of students.

Feedback is defined as knowledge regarding particular elements of one's performance or understanding provided by a mediator (e.g., educator, peer group, work, a family member, individuality, knowledge). Constructive guidance might be given by a family member or instructor, another person might give a different method, an educational resource may provide more information to make concepts easier to understand. As a result of performance, a student might check the answer to see whether or not the response was correct. Feedback provided to the learner regarding how they accomplished a learning task is known as in-context criticism, and it generally comes with the intention of helping them do better. It could be anything from a test to a short speech given in class. It's not only a specific form of communication; it may also be thought of as an aspect of a conversation. Positive feedback is a crucial aspect of interpersonal interaction that helps the person giving it, the person who receives it, and the community as a whole.

The following five factors illustrate the significance of feedback in communication competencies:

1. Feedback are always received.
2. Effective listening can also be referred to as feedback.
3. Feedback provide a chance to encourage others
4. Getting feedback is important to boosting skills.
5. Feedback encourages you to continue developing.

Feedback is a showing of support, not condemnation. When we want to raise performance to a considerable level, we should approach it positively. The language which we use plays a big role here. It is more like "If you had done...it would have," rather than "You didn't do" or "What more do you believe you could have done, given the low score?"

Students are prone to making mistakes from time to time, making inaccurate assumptions, and communicating in ways that could be unclear to others and possibly rude. Giving them feedback is what it takes to ensure that they stop making mistakes.

Listed below are some affective feedback principals:

- Support in defining effective results (goal, demands, and norms).

- Stimulate "time and dedication" in difficult educational assignments.
- Provide learners with accurate information regarding feedback in order that they can make corrections on their own.
- Enhance confidence and positive inspirational beliefs.
- Boost peer and teacher/student communication and involvement/about learning.
- Encourage the growth of reflective practices and self-evaluation in the learning process.
- Allow students to choose the processes and content of their assessments.
- Engage students in the process of selecting on assessment methods and regulations.
- Promote the developing in educational organizations.
- Assist professionals in changing their teaching methods in accordance with the requirements of their students

Actually, we are constantly surrounded with feedback. When we talk or listen to someone else, we convey feedback through our voice and word choice. Depending on how much we respect, how much we adore, or even how much we hate the person to whom we are providing feedback. If we believe we are not doing, we most likely aren't managing the communication in an effective manner. Another term for attentive listening is feedback.

Humans require extremely basic experiences before they can communicate with each other. They have to assume that what they said has a level of significance and that they have to realize that they must be listened. If you take away any of these elements, the speaker will become disoriented or perhaps irritated. By providing feedback, we express our abilities ("I understand," "OK," "I have a similar problem"). Receiving feedback creates a possibility for inspiration. Encouragement from others motivates someone to perform more effectively on more tasks. Teachers at the independent nonprofit "Interlingual" extracurricular education organization hold students accountable for their remarks and suggestions to one another, actively teach

students how to give constructive feedback to one another, and models and role-play effective feedback-giving techniques.

An author's intense emotional-communicative course is used to teach several fundamental concepts in adult groups:

- Understand the value of evaluation and feedback.
- Always willing to listen to criticism and assessment.
- Understand proper feedback.
- Provide comments at the appropriate time and position.
- Recognize your goals for learning.
- Be certain of your words.
- Be clear and straight-forward.
- Give an explanation for your actions.
- Provide comments for how to make things better.
- Analyze the feedback that you've received.

When discussing written feedback, it must be provided promptly, ensuring that it is prepared in a way that connects as closely as possible with the event and written in a format that is easily understood by students. Practical written feedback is necessary to enable the student to make improvements that are required. It isn't like "good" or "bad"; instead, it's all about the objectives and areas in which students need to grow. Feedback can be made both during and after teaching. It needs to focus on what students should learn (learning requirements) and how they should approach it (achievement requirements). In addition to offering strategies to support the student's improvement, feedback should clarify how and why the student fulfilled or failed to fulfill the demands. Positive feedback enables us to evaluate our work.

We have to welcome feedback at all times.

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